

FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JÜLICH

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The basis for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) at German universities is the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) issued in 2006. It defines forms of discrimination, explicitly including sexual harassment, and obliges higher education institutions (HEIs) to establish a complaints unit for any discrimination-related issues. However, the AGG only includes employees, not students. In addition to national legislation, HEIs have to comply with regional laws and can create their own regulations. At present, there are over 400 HEIs in Germany, and there are no systematic data available on how many have developed regulations on GBV (Kocher & Porsche 2015). According to a survey conducted among HEIs, 54% of participating HEIs had established a complaints unit for cases of discrimination according to the AGG by 2016 (Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes 2020).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

In the past seven years, Forschungszentrum Jülich has issued two documents that relate to gender-based violence: 1) Respectful Conduct at Forschungszentrum Jülich, as part of a one-off email communication sent by the Board of Directors to all employees; and 2) Dealing with Sexual Harassment in the Workplace (Umgang mit Sexueller Belästigung am Arbeitsplatz). Only the second of these two is exclusively dedicated to GBV.

Gender-based violence was first addressed at FZJ in a document called 'Respectful Conduct at FZJ', which was sent to all employees in 2015 by the Board of Directors as part of a one-off e-mail communication. The text was structured into two parts: The first part established respectful conduct as beneficial for employees and briefly defined discrimination, mobbing, and sexual harassment. The second part of the text described the kinds of action that victims and bystanders can take. It also highlighted the responsibility of people in executive, management, and training positions for recognising and preventing conflicts, encouraging respectful conduct, and pursuing relevant complaints and warnings. Finally, it stated the right of employees to lodge a complaint and provided a list of resources for witnesses and victims. Dealing with Sexual Harassment in the Workplace is considered the main policy document on GBV at FZJ. The document has the form of an informational leaflet. The institutional policy puts into effect the General Equal Treatment Act.

URLs

Neither of the two documents is available online.

Entry into force: The one-off e-mail was sent in 2015 and the policy came into force in 2019.

TRAINING

At FZJ, the following stakeholders have been trained to deal with issues of sexual harassment: The Office for Equal Opportunity, the Complaints Office, a Works Council member, and two social workers in charge of counselling. In addition, the one-off e-mail reads: 'Special training courses can offer support in acquiring and enhancing respectful conduct as well as in questioning past behavioural patterns. All employees, but because of their responsibilities those in executive positions especially, have the opportunity to take part in such training courses. Courses in communication, dealing with stress and conflict resolution, are available as part of the training programme offered by Human Resources Development. Special courses on leadership are available for executive employees'. At the beginning of 2022 tailored training courses to educate and empower employees in dealing with sexual harassment were introduced for contact point staff, employees in leadership or key functions, and all other employees who are interested and can serve as multipliers.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two documents combined address the following **four** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and online violence. The one-off e-mail focused on all four, while the policy addresses the two forms of harassment and online violence.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The two documents combined address the following **6Ps**: prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnership, and policy. While both address protection and provision of services, the one-off e-mail addresses prevention and partnership and the policy document addresses prosecution and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Both documents address two target groups: academic staff and non-academic staff. Students are not addressed.

Intersectionality addressed

No.

Specific vulnerable groups: The policy document does not specify any vulnerable group, while the one-off e-mail mentions that people with past negative experiences may be especially sensitive. It also provides the contact information for a disabled persons' representative although people with disabilities are not mentioned anywhere else in the document.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. Both documents address bystanders. The one-off e-mail reads: 'People who are not involved but notice something is wrong are asked to show solidarity and responsibility by offering the victims help and support in finding a solution.' The other policy document invites bystanders to support affected persons if they witness sexual harassment and states how they can do so.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Both documents set out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigation. The one-off e-mail focuses on violence among staff members while the policy document Dealing with Sexual Harassment in the Workplace sets out one procedure for all.

The one-off e-mail defines: who to contact and how to report. The policy document defines who to contact.

One-off e-mail Respectful Conduct at FZJ

Who to contact: The document includes a list of internal contacts. These are for social counselling, medical service, the Equal Opportunities Bureau, the Complaints Office, and the disabled persons' representatives.

How to report: Every employee has the right to lodge a complaint if they feel disadvantaged or discriminated against. Also, equal opportunities officers, their representatives, the Works Council, and disabled persons' representatives can also be contacted. The contact details are available on the intranet.

Dealing with sexual harassment in the workplace

Who to contact:

- Complaints Office – legal review – case-related measures
- Works Council – representation of interests – advice and support – prevention
- Works Council member you can trust
- Office for Equal Opportunity – referral
- Equal Opportunity Office – representation of interests
- Advice and Support – prevention
- Social counselling – psychosocial counselling, possible courses of action

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researchers Monica Perez and Friederike Kressner in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

